

Automated Identification of Self-Admitted Technical Debt in Source Code with Machine Learning

This supplementary document is provided alongside the article titled "Automated Identification of Self-Admitted Technical Debt in Source Code with Machine Learning." It covers the results obtained in the Rapid Review. If you have any specific questions or need clarification regarding the content of the document, please feel free to share more details or ask specific questions. We are here to help!

Table C1 presents the 33 publications selected after the second filter, as established in the Rapid Review protocol.

Table C1 - List of Selected Articles.

ID	Article	Author(s)	Year	Publication Source
P01	A Systematic Literature Review on Technical Debt Prioritization: Strategies, Processes, Factors and Tools	V. Lenarduzzi, T. Besker, D. Taibi, A. Martini, and F. Fontana	2021	Journal of Systems and Software
P02	Analyzing strategies for identifying technical debt	I. Oliveira, H. Marques, and L. Xavier	2020	Workshop on Visualization, Evolution, and Software Maintenance
P03	An Empirical Study on Self-Admitted Technical Debt in Dockerfiles	M. Iammarino, F. Zampetti, L. Aversano, and M. Penta	2022	Empirical Software Engineering
P04	An Empirical Study on the Co- Occurrence Between Refactoring Actions and Self-Admitted Technical Debt Removal	H. Azuma, S. Matsumoto, Y. Kamei, and S. Kusumoto	2021	Journal of Systems and Software
P05	An Overview and Comparison of Technical Debt Measurement Tools	P. Avgeriou, D. Taibi, A. Ampatzoglou, F. Fontana, T. Besker, A. Chatzigeorgiou, V. Lenarduzzi, A. Martini, A. Moschou, I. Pigazzini, N. Saarimaki, D. Sas, S. Toledo, and A. Tsintzira	2021	IEEE Software
P06	Architectural Technical Debt in Microservices	S. Toledo, A. Martini, A. Przybyszewska, and D. Sjøberg	2019	International Conference on Technical Debt
P07	ATDx: Building an Architectural Technical Debt Index	R. Verdecchia, P. Lago, I. Malavolta, and I. Ozkaya.	2020	International Conference on Evaluation of Novel Approaches to Software Engineering
P08	Automating Change-Level Self- Admitted Technical Debt Determination	M. Yan, X. Xia, E. Shihab, D. Lo, J. Yin, and X. Yang,	2018	IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering
P09	A Tertiary Study on Technical Debt: Types, Management Strategies, Research Trends, and base Information for Practitioners	N. Rios, M. Neto, and R. Spínola	2018	Information and Software Technology
P10	Common Causes and Effects of Technical Debt in Serbian IT: InsignTD Survey Replication	R. Ramač, V. Mandić, N. Taušan, N. Rios, M. Neto, C. Seaman, and R. Spínola	020	Euromicro Conference on Software Engineering and Advanced Applications

P11	Conceptualisation of Using Technical Debt 2 to Measure the Innovation Level of New Product – 3 Selected Issues	P. Paweł	2021	Scientific Papers of Silesian University of Technology
P12	Embracing Technical Debt, from a Startup Company Perspective	T. Besker, A. Martini, R. Lokuge, K. Blincoe, and J. Bosch	2018	International Conference on Software Maintenance and Evolution
P13	Familiarity, Causes and Reactions of Software Practitioners to the Presence of Technical Debt: A Replicated Study in the Chilean Software Industry	B. Pérez, J. Brito, H. Astudillo, D. Correal, N. Rios, R. Spínola, M. Mendonça, and C. Seaman	2019	International Conference of the Chilean Computer Science Society
P14	How do Developers Fix Issues and Pay Back Technical Debt in the Apache Ecosystem?	G. Digkas, M. Lungu, P. Avgeriou, A. Chatzigeorgiou, and A. Ampatzoglou	2018	International Conference on Software Analysis, Evolution and Reengineering
P15	Identifying Design and Requirement Self-Admitted Technical Debt using N-gram IDF	S. Wattanakriengkrai, R. Maipradit, H. Hata, M. Choetkiertikul, T. Sunetnanta, and K. Matsumoto	2018	International Workshop on Empirical Software Engineering in Practice
P16	Increasing Awareness for Potential Technical Debt in the Engineering of Production Systems	F. Ocker, M. Seitz, M. Oligschläger, M. Zou, and B. Vogel-Heuser	2019	International Conference on Industrial Informatics
P17	Introducing the Concept of Technical Debt to Smart Grids: A System Engineering Perspective	J. Schütz and M. Uslar	2019	International Conference and Exhibition on Electricity Distribution
P18	Investigating the Point of View of Project Management Practitioners on Technical Debt - A Study on Stack Exchange	F. Gomes, E. Santos, S. Freire, M. Mendonça, T. Mendes, and R. Spínola	2022	In Proceedings of the International Conference on Technical Debt
P19	Managing Architectural Technical Debt: A Unified Model and Systematic Literature Review	T. Besker, A. Martini, and J. Bosch	2018	Journal of Systems and Software
P20	Preventing Technical Debt with the TAP Framework for Technical Debt Aware Management	M. Wiese, P. Rachw, M. Riebisch, and J. Schwarze	2022	Information and Software Technology
P21	Security Risk Assessment and Management as Technical Debt	K. Rindell and J. Holvitie	2019	International Conference on Cyber Security and Protection of Digital Services
P22	Technical Debt and Agile Software Development Practices and Processes: An Industry Practitioner Survey	J. Holvitie and V. Leppänen	2018	Information and Software Technology
P23	Technical Debt Aware Estimations in Software Engineering: A Systematic Mapping Study	P. Klimczyk and L. Madeyski	2020	e-Informatica Software Engineering Journal
P24	Technical Debt in Hardware Systems and Elements	L. Rosser and Z. Ouzzif	2021	IEEE Aerospace Conference

P25	Technical Debt in Large-Scale Distributed Projects: An Industrial Case Study	A. Sousa, L. Rocha, R. Britto, Z. Gong, and F. Lyu	2021	International Conference on Software Analysis, Evolution and Reengineering
P26	Technical Debt Management Automation: State of the Art and Future Perspectives	J. Biazotto, D. Feitosa, P. Avgeriou, and E. Nakagawa	2023	Information and Software Technology
P27	Technical Debt Prioritization: Taxonomy, Methods Results and Practical Characteristics	D. Pina, A. Goldman, and G. Tonin	2021	Euromicro Conference on Software Engineering and Advanced Applications
P28	Technical Debt Tracking: Current State of practice: A Survey and Multiple Case Study in 15 Large Organizations	A. Martini, T. Besker, and J. Bosch	2018	Science of Computer Programming
P29	The Lifecycle of Technical Debt that Manifests in Both Source Code and Issue Trackers	J. Tan, D. Feitosa, and P. Avgeriou	2023	Information and Software Technology
P30	The Role of Awareness and Gamification on Technical Debt Management	Y. Crespo, C. Lopez-Nozal, R. Marticorena-Sanchez, M. Gonzalo-Tasis, and M. Piattini	2022	Information and Software Technology
P31	Toward a Technical Debt Conceptualization for Serverless Computing	V. Lenarduzzi, J. Daly, A. Martini, S. Panichella, and D. Tamburri	2021	IEEE Software
P32	An analysis of the relationship between code smells and self-admitted technical debt	F. Gomes, T. Mendes, R. Spínola, M. Mendonça, and M. Farias	2019	Workshop on Visualization, Evolution, and Software Maintenance
P33	Who (Self) Admits Technical Debt?	G. Fucci, F. Zampetti, A. Serebrenik, and M. Penta	2020	International Conference on Software Maintenance and Evolution

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